

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ADAPTATION AND INTEGRATION OF INTERNATIONAL STUDENT MIGRANTS

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Abstract

The article examines current issues related to the adaptation and integration of international students and migrants. Research evidence indicates that migration movements lead to significant changes in interpersonal relationships, social status, lifestyle patterns, and established systems of interaction with the surrounding environment. These changes inevitably require a reconsideration of attitudes, relationships, and perceptions of social roles and their adequacy in newly formed situations.

The successful adaptation and integration of international students depend on the integration of methods that positively influence adaptation processes, such as language proficiency or bilingualism and the development of professional competencies, which enhance employability opportunities. Education and professional training are among the most significant instruments of integration.

Keywords: higher education institution, adaptation, integration, migration, international students, intercultural adaptation.

The current economic situation, political and social conflicts, and the geopolitical developments of recent decades have led to large-scale population migration worldwide. Issues of migrant adaptation and integration remain highly relevant and require comprehensive social, economic, and sociocultural solutions aimed at integrating this population group into host societies.

At present, globalization increasingly encompasses various spheres of life, erasing borders and facilitating transformations in both the economy and the education system. Growing international mobility driven by globalization has made experiences of working and studying in diverse cultural and academic environments much more common [Tajibayeva Zh. et al, 2025]. Many young people choose to pursue modern knowledge and skills through education abroad, as universities offer more diverse academic programs and broader opportunities.

International students represent a specific category of temporary migrants who arrive primarily for educational purposes; however, student migration is often closely linked to labor migration, as many students engage in part-time employment during their studies. International academic mobility of students is more relevant than ever, with its scale increasing annually, leading to the emergence of so-called “educational nomads.” The stay of international students is regulated by national migration legislation, visa regulations, and permitted durations of residence. When considering student migration, it is important to note its economic benefits for host countries and its significance for universities, where the enrollment of international students

serves as an indicator of institutional prestige. International students not only acquire education but also internalize new values, shaping their worldview, attitudes, and social relations. For higher education institutions, one of the key challenges is the adaptation and integration of international students into a new sociocultural environment.

From a scientific and theoretical perspective, an important concept in the study of personality adaptation to a different ethnic and sociocultural environment is the notion that entering a new culture is often accompanied by profound psychological upheaval, commonly referred to as “cultural shock.”

According to Ward C., Kennedy A. (1993) cultural shock is “the shock of encountering a new and unfamiliar culture,” which is often perceived as unpleasant due to its unexpected nature and its potential to provoke negative evaluations of one’s own culture.

Researchers such as Berry J.W., Sam D.L., Adler P.S. (2006) argue that despite its association with negative experiences, cultural shock can also have a positive impact on personal growth. This may manifest in the acquisition of new values, attitudes, and behavioral patterns. Through direct experience in a different cultural environment, individuals gain knowledge that fosters awareness of the sources of their own ethnocentrism and promotes new perspectives on human diversity.

In this regard, cultural shock can play a constructive role when international students and migrants are open to accepting new values and behavioral models, ultimately serving as a source of self-development and self-improvement. The intensity of cultural shock is

typically expressed through symptoms such as confusion, discomfort, loneliness, feelings of rejection or being an outsider in a new group, difficulty accepting moral norms, clothing, or food, challenges in self-identification, fear of social contact, language barriers, heightened anxiety, feelings of incompetence, and nostalgia for one's homeland and close relatives.

Social adaptation represents a type of interaction between an individual or group and the social environment in which the requirements and expectations of social actors are aligned with their capabilities and the realities of the social context. The essence of social adaptation for foreigners temporarily residing in a host country lies in their ability to preserve and maintain a familiar lifestyle while accepting a foreign culture—not through assimilation, but through respect for the host country's laws, traditions, values, norms, and mentality.

Contemporary researchers (Ward & Kennedy; Sam; Phinney) generally agree that adaptation to a new social environment often proceeds through four stages:

1. Initial stage, characterized by awareness of the need to change behavior in accordance with the new environment, while individuals or groups continue to adhere to their original value system.
2. Tolerance stage, where mutual tolerance and respect for differing value systems and behavioral patterns emerge between individuals, groups, and the host society.
3. Accommodation, involving acceptance of the core elements of the host society's value system while retaining certain values of one's original culture that may also be recognized by the new environment.
4. Assimilation, marked by full convergence of value systems between individuals, groups, and the host society.

Studying abroad attracts international students due to the quality of education, strong institutional reputations, and enhanced career prospects. Language proficiency plays a crucial role not only in academic success but also in the development of career-related competencies and work motivation among international students.

Sonnenschein K., Wiik R. (2025), in their study of international students' adaptation in Norway, demonstrated that knowledge of the Norwegian language, networking at job fairs, and awareness of future career opportunities are critical for employment and integration. Although students prioritized the development of oral language skills, many experienced difficulties improving them due to limited opportunities for practical language use both inside and outside the classroom. The study also found that an internal locus of control in language learning positively influences the development of professional competencies. The authors recommend placing greater emphasis on oral practice in language courses and introducing language exchange programs to strengthen interaction between local and international students.

Language proficiency is a fundamental component of the integration process, and insufficient language skills significantly and negatively affect both academic performance and social relationships (Tajibayeva et al., 2025). Therefore, language support programs and initiatives aimed at enhancing cultural

awareness play a decisive role in integrating immigrant students into universities. The presence of social support mechanisms strengthens students' sense of belonging and facilitates adaptation processes (Shergill, 1997). English, in particular, has been identified as vital for networking, enhancing "knowing whom," and effectively performing work tasks (Itani et al., 2015).

Language skills contribute to the formation of personal and professional networks, reinforcing professional competence. Language functions as a key tool of social interaction within organizations, providing access to information and relationships that foster professional growth (Itani et al., 2015). Moreover, language skills shape personal and professional identity and influence work motivation, aligning with components of professional competencies. Research also indicates that bilingualism facilitates access to managerial positions and workplace success in Northern European countries, whereas lack of language proficiency is perceived as a major barrier to career advancement. Thus, bilingualism can be considered an integral part of professional identity.

Professional competencies are defined by Akkermans, J., Brenninkmeijer, V., Huibers, M., & Blonk, R. W. B. (2013) as "knowledge, skills, and abilities that are central to career development and can be influenced and developed by individuals themselves." While the importance of professional competencies for mobility across organizations and cultural contexts is widely recognized, relatively few studies have examined the role of language in career mobility (Itani et al., 2015). Research findings suggest that well-developed language skills support the formation of professional competencies that facilitate mobility, intersecting with all three components of the career competencies model.

For immigrant students, adaptation to university life extends beyond academic achievement and includes the establishment of social relationships, identity reconstruction, and understanding of cultural diversity. In educational environments characterized by high pedagogical competence, students are more likely to successfully navigate these processes. Multicultural classroom discussions and group projects enable students to understand diverse perspectives and develop cultural empathy (Braxton et al., 2013). The effective integration of psychological adaptation and pedagogical competence enriches students' university experience. With appropriate support from educators, students can achieve progress not only academically but also socially and personally, which in the long term contributes to professional success and societal participation (Ward & Kennedy, 1999).

In addition to language proficiency and professional competencies, sociocultural adaptation is crucial, as it influences personal development, performance success, and the maintenance of physical and mental health. Studies by [Alkar E.](#), [Atasoy E.](#) (2024) examining the relationship between cultural intelligence and acculturation levels of international students show that those with higher cultural intelligence communicate more effectively, adapt successfully, exhibit higher self-esteem and openness, and demonstrate moderate levels of acculturation.

The organization of the educational process, pedagogical conditions, methods, and forms of instruction that support international students' adaptation during professional training are of particular importance. Psychological and pedagogical support for international students should be implemented through coordinated efforts involving academic advisors, faculty, student self-governance bodies, and the students themselves.

Socio-psychological support for migrants, based on systematic and consistent implementation of corrective and developmental interventions that account for intercultural adaptation factors, can significantly reduce maladaptation and social tension. Thus, successful integration requires meaningful interaction between migrants and the host society, underscoring the fact that integration should be understood as a two-way process.

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